

LINEAR-CIRCULAR DICHROISM AND ONE-PHOTON ABSORPTION IN PIEZOELECTRIC SEMICONDUCTORS WITH COHERENT SATURATION EFFECTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14161758>

Abstract. *The dependence of the contribution of saturation effect in one-photon light absorption coefficient in semiconductors with a band structure, consisting of two close posed sub-bands surveyed, one of which has "camel's back" structure, from a radiation intensity. Thus "nonlinearity" - saturation of one-photon absorption of polarized light is taken into discounted. It is shown that this nonlinearity is stipulated in main change in a field of electromagnetic wave of the "resonant" electronic transition in light absorption coefficient.*

Keywords: *one-photon light absorption, matrix element, polarization, optical transition, hole, valence zone, semiconductor.*

Аннотация. *Рассмотрена зависимость вклада эффекта насыщения в коэффициент однофотонного поглощения света в полупроводниках с зонной структурой, состоящей из двух близко расположенных подзон, одна из которых имеет "горбообразная" структура, от интенсивности излучения. При этом учтена «нелинейность» - насыщение однофотонного поглощения поляризованного света. Показано, что эта нелинейность обусловлена в основном изменением в поле сильной электромагнитной волны «резонансного» электронного вклада в коэффициент поглощения света.*

Ключевые слова: *однофотонное поглощение света, матричный элемент, поляризация, оптический переход, дырки, валентная зона, полупроводник.*

Annotatsiya. *tor zonalni yarimo tkazgichlarda yorug‘lik intensivligiga bog‘liq ravishda bir fotonli yorug‘lik yutilish koeffitsiyentiga to‘yinish effektining hissasi o‘rganilgan. Shu bilan birga, qutblangan yorug‘likning bir fotonli yutilishida kuzatiladigan "nochiziqli" - ya'ni to‘yinish holati hisobga olingan. Ushbu nochiziqli yutilish asosan kuchli elektromagnit to‘lqin maydonida yorug‘lik yutilish koeffitsiyentiga "rezonansli" elektron ulushining o‘zgarishi bilan bog‘liq ekani ko‘rsatilgan.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *bir fotonli yorug‘lik yutilishi, matritsa elementi, qutblanish, optik o‘tish, teshiklar, valent zona, yarimo tkazgich.*

Linear-circular dichroism in one-photon absorption of light in piezoelectric semiconductors: accounting for the coherent saturation effect. With the advent of lasers that generate intense submillimeter-range radiation (see, for example, [1]), new aspects of electromagnetic radiation interaction with solid materials have emerged, particularly multi-photon light absorption in semiconductors [2,3]. In the spherical approximation of the energy spectrum of charge carriers, one-photon nonlinear absorption of infrared (IR) and submillimeter radiation in semiconductors with a band structure composed of two closely spaced branches is discussed in [4]. It is shown that the light absorption coefficient decreases with increasing light intensity. A uniform perspective on the mechanism of one-photon light absorption nonlinearity in semiconductors with a degenerate valence band, depending on the degree of light polarization, is presented in [2-4].

However, the question of linear-circular dichroism in light absorption in a gyrotropic medium remains open. Therefore, we will examine below the contribution of saturation effects to the one-photon light absorption coefficient in semiconductors with a band structure composed of two closely spaced subbands, one of which exhibits a "hump-like" structure, depending on the intensity of the radiation. In this case, we will consider the "nonlinearity" - the saturation of one-photon absorption of polarized light (PL). This nonlinearity is primarily due to the change in the "resonant" electronic contribution to the light absorption coefficient in the field of a strong electromagnetic wave.

The one-photon light absorption coefficient $K^{(1)}$ can conveniently be defined using the off-diagonal component of the density matrix ρ :

$$\rho = \begin{pmatrix} \rho_{11} & \rho_{12} \\ \rho_{21} & \rho_{22} \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Here, $\rho_{21} = \rho_{(2,m;1,3m)}$ and $\rho_{22} = \rho_{(2,m;2,m)}$, $\rho_{11} = \rho_{(1,3m;1,3m)}$ are the off-diagonal and diagonal components of the density matrix $\hat{\rho}$, which satisfy the system of equations

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\rho}_{ll} &= -(-1)^l \frac{2}{\hbar} |M_{3m,m}^{(1)}| + I_{ll}^+ + I_{ll}^- + I_{l-l}^+ + I_{l-l}^-, \\ \dot{\rho}_{12}^{(0)} - \Gamma \rho_{12}^{(0)} &= \frac{i}{\hbar} [(E_{1k} - E_{2k} - \hbar\omega) \rho_{12}^{(0)} + 2 |M_{3m,m}^{(1)}| (\rho_{22} - \rho_{11})], \quad (\rho_{12} = \rho_{12}^{(0)} e^{i\alpha x}) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $\Gamma = \frac{(T_{1\vec{k}} + T_{21\vec{k}})}{2T_1 T_2}$, and $I_{(ll')}^\pm$ are the incoming "+" and outgoing "-" collision integrals of holes due to lattice inhomogeneities or mutual interactions (with $l \neq l' = 1, 2$). Here, T_1 and T_2 are the relaxation times of hole momentum in the resonance region. The angular momentum projections onto the direction of the wave vector \vec{k} with $m' = 3m = \pm 3/2$ correspond to the states $(1, \vec{k})$ in the light-hole subband.

Since there is an analogy between the optical transitions of electrons between subbands in the conduction band of a semiconductor and the optical transitions in two-level systems, equations (2) are analogous to the equations for a two-level quantum system with a transition frequency of $\frac{(E_{1\vec{k}} - E_{2\vec{k}})}{\hbar}$, and damping constants $T_{1\vec{k}}^{-1}$ and $T_{2\vec{k}}^{-1}$ [4].

If we take into account that the resonance region has a width of $\hbar\Gamma$, then in the case of $\tilde{\omega} \gg \Gamma$

$$(3)$$

it is straightforward to obtain

$$K_1' = K_1 \frac{1}{4\pi} \int d\Omega_{\vec{k}} \left(\frac{|e_+'|^2}{\sqrt{1 + a^2 |e_+'|^2}} + \frac{|e_-'|^2}{\sqrt{1 + |e_-'|^2}} \right) \frac{1}{|e_+'|^2 \cdot 2} \quad (4)$$

where ω is the frequency of the acoustic phonon,

$$K_1' = K_1 \frac{3}{8} \int_{-1}^{+1} d\cos \theta \left(\frac{|e_+'|^2}{\sqrt{1 + a^2 |e_+'|^2}} + \frac{|e_-'|^2}{\sqrt{1 + a^2 |e_-'|^2}} \right) \quad (5)$$

K_1 is the "linear" (nonlinearity not accounted for) light absorption coefficient for direct optical transitions between subbands in the conduction band of the semiconductor. For $|e_{\pm}'|^2 = \frac{2}{3}$, this is the angularly averaged value of $|e_{\pm}|^2$ over the wave vector \vec{k} . Here, $a = \frac{I}{I_c}$, where $I_c = \frac{2cn\omega m_1 m_2 \hbar \omega}{3\pi(m_1 - m_2)e^2 T_{1\vec{k}} T_{2\vec{k}}}$ is the critical intensity of light. For an arbitrary light intensity I , the probability of inter-subband optical transitions per unit volume can be represented as

$$W^{(1)} = \frac{4\pi^2 \alpha I}{n_\omega \hbar \omega b^2 k_{zc}} \sum_{\vec{k}} f(E_{1\vec{k}}) (1 - e^{-\beta \hbar \omega}) \frac{|e_z|^2 \delta(E_{2\vec{k}} - E_{1\vec{k}} - \hbar \omega)}{\varepsilon (1 + I \varphi |e_z|^2 / (\varepsilon I_S))^{1/2}}, \quad (6)$$

where

$$I_S = \omega^2 T_1 T_2 I_0, \quad I_0 = \frac{\hbar^3 \omega^4 n_\omega}{8\pi \alpha b^2}, \quad \varepsilon = (\Delta^2 + b^2 k_z^2)^{1/2} \quad (7)$$

$\beta = \frac{1}{k_B T}$, where T is the temperature, and k_B is the Boltzmann constant. The function $f(E)$ represents the distribution of charge carriers with energy E , while α is the fine structure parameter $\left(\frac{e^2}{\hbar c}\right)$, and n_ω is the refractive index of the medium at frequency ω . T_l is the escape time of charge carriers from the resonance region in branch l [2]. The parameter b is a zone parameter that acts as a multiplier for the term linear in the wave vector in the effective Hamiltonian (see, for example, [5,6]). In the case of n -type GaP, $b = P$ and $\phi = \Delta$ [6]; for tellurium, $b = \beta_V$ and $\phi = \beta_V k_z$.

The electron energy in the final state $E_1^{(1)}$, determined by the energy conservation law between the initial and final electron states, is defined by the frequency of the exciting light. For example, in the spherical approximation of the electron energy spectrum: $E_{l\vec{k}} = \frac{\hbar^2 k^2}{2m_l} + (-1)^l \frac{\Delta}{2}$, we have: $E_1^{(1)} = \frac{(\hbar \omega - \Delta) m_2}{m_1 - m_2}$ where Δ is the energy gap between the subbands of the conduction band in the center of the Brillouin zone. In our case, the expression for the interband matrix element of the momentum operator can be written as:

$$\vec{e} \vec{p}_{21} = \frac{m_0}{\hbar} e_z b \frac{\varphi}{\varepsilon} \quad (8)$$

where \vec{e} is the polarization vector of the light. Then, by substituting (8) and the expressions for the energy spectrum that account for the "hump" in the lower subband:

$$E_{i\vec{k}} = A k_z^2 + B k_\perp^2 + (-1)^l \sqrt{\Delta^2 + b^2 k_z^2}, \quad (k_\perp^2 = k_x^2 + k_y^2), \quad (9)$$

into (6) and performing the summation over k , we obtain an expression for the probability of one-photon optical transition as a function of the degree of light polarization

$$W_{\text{lin}}^{(1)} / W_0^{(1)} = \xi_{\text{lin}}(I/I_S), \quad (10)$$

$$W_{\text{circ}}^{(1)} / W_0^{(1)} = \xi_{\text{circ}}(I/2I_S), \quad (11)$$

where $B = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m_\perp}$, $A = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m_\parallel}$, $k_z = \frac{1}{b} \sqrt{m}$, and m_\perp and m_\parallel are the transverse and longitudinal effective masses of the charge carriers. The expression for the probability of a one-photon transition $W_0^{(1)}$ is given by

$$W_0^{(1)} = \frac{\alpha}{n_\omega B} \frac{I}{(\hbar \omega)^2} f(E_\omega) (1 - e^{-\beta \hbar \omega}) \frac{b}{\phi_0},$$

where $E_\omega = E_{1\vec{k}}(k_\perp = 0, k_z = k_z C)$, $\phi_0 = \phi(k_z = k_z C)$, and $2\Delta = E_{2\vec{k}} - E_{1\perp k}$ is the energy difference between the conduction band subbands at the center of the Brillouin zone

$$\xi_{\text{lin}}(X) = \frac{1}{4x} \left[2\sqrt{1+x} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{x}} \ln \left| \frac{\sqrt{1+x} + \sqrt{x}}{\sqrt{1+x} - \sqrt{x}} \right| \right] \quad (x = I/I_S) \quad (12a)$$

$$\xi_{\text{circ}}(Y) = \frac{1}{4y} \left[1 + \frac{y-1}{\sqrt{y}} \arcsin \sqrt{\frac{y}{1+y}} \right] \quad (y = x/2) \quad (12b)$$

the asymptotic form in the regions of low and high light intensity, which can be represented similarly to (12a, b):

$$\xi_{\text{lin}}(x) = \begin{cases} 1/3 & \text{for } x \ll 1 \\ 1/2\sqrt{x} & \text{for } x \gg 1 \end{cases} \quad (13a)$$

$$\xi_{\text{circ}}(y) = \begin{cases} 1/3 & \text{for } y \ll 1 \\ \pi/8\sqrt{y} & \text{for } y \gg 1 \end{cases} \quad (13b)$$

We interpret the mechanism of linear-circular dichroism in inter-subband nonlinear light absorption in semiconductors with a "hump-like" band structure, accompanied by one-photon optical transitions of charge carriers between subbands located at the center of the Brillouin zone. According to the latest relations, the probability of these optical transitions under linearly polarized excitation is described by formulas (12a, 13a), and in the case of circularly polarized light excitation by formulas (12b, 13b). In this process, the momentum alignment of charge carriers occurs when illuminated by linearly polarized radiation. When $\vec{k} \parallel \vec{\chi}$ (where $\vec{\chi}$ is the wave vector of the photon), according to the conservation law of angular momentum projection, alignment occurs only for linear polarization instead of circular.

According to (12a, b) and (13a, b), the directional diagrams in two planes of k -space, containing the vector \vec{e} , are not generally identical in light intensity. In the region of low light intensity, where photoinduced changes in the charge carrier distribution function can be neglected, the directional diagrams become indistinguishable, and the probabilities of one-photon optical transitions do not depend on the polarization degree.

According to (10) and (11), the factor of linear-circular dichroism $\eta = \frac{W_{\text{circ}}^{(1)}}{W_{\text{lin}}^{(1)}}$ at high intensity, i.e., $I \gg I_0$, does not depend on intensity and equals $\frac{\pi\sqrt{2}}{4} \approx 1.1$ (see, for example, [4]). At the frequency Δ/\hbar , two-photon linear-circular dichroism in semiconductors with a "hump-like" band structure arises only when considering the resonant saturation of the relevant optical transitions, with its features depending on light intensity, similarly to one-photon nonlinear absorption.

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